

Comparison of Nutritional Status in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients under Hemodialysis vs. Non-dialysis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Protein-energy wasting is common in chronic kidney disease patients, those who are on maintenance Hemodialysis. Chronic kidney disease is an inflammatory state, and as the disease progresses, the nutritional status of patients is influenced by low protein intake, metabolic acidosis, uremia, etc. Hence, this study aimed to compare the nutritional status of chronic kidney disease patients under dialysis and non-dialysis.

Methods: In this single-center cross-sectional comparative study conducted in Patan Hospital, the nutritional status of patients who were on maintenance hemodialysis was compared with stage III, IV, and V chronic kidney disease patients using subjective goal assessment methods along with anthropometric and biochemical measurements.

Results: A total of 143 participants were included in this study. (74 in the Dialysis group and 69 in the non-dialysis chronic kidney disease group). The mean age of the study population was 50 years in the dialysis group and 47 years in the non-dialysis group. 77.03% of patients in the maintenance hemodialysis group were found to be mild to moderately malnourished compared to 39.13% in the non-dialysis group, which was significant (p-value 0.000009). Anthropometric and biochemical values were statistically significant in the non-dialysis group of various stages (p-value less than 0.05).

Conclusion: Malnutrition increases as chronic kidney disease progresses and is more evident in patients under dialysis. Early dietary counseling with a dietician is recommended. Clinicians should address the underlying inflammatory state, correct anemia, and advise adequate nutritional protein to prevent malnutrition.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease; Nutrition; Subject goal assessment; hemodialysis; CKD; SGA

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD), often leading to a gradual and irreparable loss of renal function, is common enough to be considered a worldwide public health threat.^[1] A prevalence of 14.5% has been reported in Europe, Australia, and Asia.^[2] Protein-energy wasting (PEW) is common in chronic kidney disease patients, those who are on maintenance Hemodialysis (MHD).^[3] PEW is one of CKD patients' strongest predictors of morbidity and mortality. The prevalence of malnutrition in patients with MHD worldwide is 23-70%.^[4]

Several methods have been adopted for evaluating the nutritional status of HD patients for malnutrition, such as Subjective goal assessment (SGA), anthropometric parameters, biochemical values, bioelectrical impedance analysis, and dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry. The above techniques are often not practical in clinical situations because of the expense and time consumption.^[5] It is recommended to assess malnutrition by combining methods (SGA, Anthropometric parameters, biochemical parameters).^[6] The National Kidney Foundation (NKF) recommends the Subjective Goal Assessment as one of the crucial methods to implement when assessing PEM in HD patients.^[7]

In Nepal, there is a high prevalence of PEW in MHD patients. There is a lack of data on the assessment of Nutritional status in patients with CKD who are not under Dialysis and in patients under MHD. This study aimed to assess the Nutritional status of Patients under MHD in Patan Hospital and those CKD patients who are not under dialysis.

METHODS

Study design and setting

This single-center cross-sectional study was conducted at the Patan Academy of Health Sciences (PAHS) from October 2019 to September 2020. Approval of the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Committee (IRC) of PAHS.

Study participant

The sample size was calculated using the Kelsey and Fleiss formula. The confidence interval was taken to be 95%, the power of a study to be 80%, and the ratio between 2 groups was taken as 1:1. With this, the minimum sample size in each group was calculated to be 65.

All the patients in the schedule were the minimum sample size for the Dialysis group. For the non-dialysis group, patients with CKD stages 3,4 and 5 were included from Other PD and Medical Ward who fulfilled the criteria. An equal number of patients were divided in each group. Patients with Persistent Glomerular filtration rate <60ml/min/1.732m² level (CKD stage 3, 4, and 5) and patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis for at least

six months were included in the study. However, patients with active infection, severe liver disease, and gastrointestinal disease were excluded.

Study tool

CKD staging was done based on the estimated glomerular filtration (eGFR) rate estimated by using an equation developed by the chronic kidney disease Epidemiology (CKD-EPI) collaboration. The equation was applied with a calculator for the estimation of eGFR. CKD stages 1 and 2 were not included as these people might not have significant malnutrition.

Nutritional tools were used to assess the nutritional status of the patients. Nutritional tools were anthropometry, 7-point subjective goal assessment, and laboratory evaluation. One time SGA score was calculated.^[8] The 7-point SGA includes two major categories: the history and physical examination. The history portion of the 7-point SGA is comprised of five sections: weight/weight change, dietary intake, gastrointestinal symptoms, functional capacity, and disease state/co-morbidities as related to nutritional status. Each section of the 7-point SGA was rated on a scale from one to seven. Based on subjective consideration of all the scores from each category, an overall number was assigned to each patient. A six or seven indicated a very mild risk of malnutrition to the well-nourished; a three, four, or five rating determined mild to moderate malnutrition; and one or two revealed severe malnutrition. Patients were classified into one of three groups from those ratings: 1= well-nourished, 2 = moderate malnutrition, and 3 = severe malnutrition. Anthropometry evaluation was done by measuring the patient's weight, height, and mid-arm muscle circumference. Serum albumin and hemoglobin were measured, which is done routinely in our patients, and were done at the time of the interview.

Statistical analysis

Data were entered in MS Excel 2016 and Epi info version 7.2.2; analysis was done in Epi info version 7.2.2. The normality of data was tested by comparing a histogram of the sample data to a standard probability curve and using Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. The two groups' nutritional status was compared using independent sample T-tests and Mann-Whitney U test as appropriate. A one-way ANOVA test or Kruskal Wallis test, as appropriate, was used to compare more than two groups. A P-value of 0.05 or less was considered significant.

Ethics

Approval of the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Committee (IRC) of PAHS. Participants were explained about the study in detail before obtaining consent. The written consent was obtained from all participants. For written consent, a generic PAHS format in Nepali was used. If participants wished, they were allowed to withdraw at any time without any reason. We guaranteed the confidentiality of the participants.

RESULTS

There was a total of 143 patients in the study—73 in the hemodialysis group and 69 in the non-dialysis group. In the non-dialysis group, there were 23, 25, and 21 patients with CKD stage III, IV, and V, respectively. The mean age of the study population was 50 years in dialysis and 47 years in the non-dialysis group. The mean years with kidney

disease was 4.4 years in dialysis and 2.7 years in the non-dialysis group. The mean Duration of dialysis was 2.1 years (Table-1&2).

Table-1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population.

Variables	Dialysis(n=74)	Non-Dialysis(n=69)
Age in years (Mean)	50	47
Male (%)	60.81	55.07
Female (%)	39.19	44.93

Table-2: Clinical Characteristics.

Variables	Dialysis	Non-dialysis
years with kidney disease (mean)	4.4	2.7
years of dialysis (mean)	2.1	-
Co-morbidities: n (%)		
Hypertension	67(90.5%)	48(69%)
Diabetes mellitus	15(20.2%)	27(39.1%)
IgA nephropathy	3(4%)	12(17.3%)
Lupus nephritis	0	3(4.3%)

Using the SGA score, 77.03 % of people in the dialysis group were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition compared to the non-dialysis group, where the prevalence was 39.13 %. There were no patients with severe malnutrition in either of the groups.(Table 3)

Table 3: Comparison of Nutritional status using SGA score in dialysis and non-dialysis patients

	Dialysis n (%) 74	Non-dialysis n (%)	p-value
Normal nutrition	17(22.97)	42(60.87)	9E-06
Mild to moderate malnutrition	57(77.03)	27(39.13)	
Severe malnutrition	0	0	

In the non-dialysis group, none of the patients of CKD stage III were malnourished, 24% of patients of stage IV were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition, and all the patients of stage V were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition (p-value 0.00000).(Table 4)

Table-4: Comparison of nutritional status in non-dialysis patients of various stages using SGA score.

	Stage III (n =23)	Stage IV (n=25)	Stage V (n=21)	p-value
Normal nutrition	23	19	0	0
Mild to moderate malnutrition	0	6	21	

Comparing the BMI in dialysis and the non-dialysis group was not statistically significant; the Mean MAMC was higher in the non-dialysis group than in dialysis patients. (Table 5) Both groups' results were similar for Hemoglobin and albumin. (Table 6)

Table-5: Comparison of anthropometric values in dialysis and non-dialysis patients in different nutritional groups.

BMI (kg/m²) means:

	Dialysis	Non-Dialysis	P-value
Normal nutrition	21.72±1.74	21.68±1.46	0.86
Mild to moderate malnutrition	20.33±3.30	20.58±2.14	0.26

MAMC (cm) means:

	Dialysis	Non-Dialysis	P-value
Normal nutrition	21.91±2.66	24.85±3.03	0.001
Mild to moderate malnutrition	21.46±3.56	23.73±3.46	0.038

Table-6: Comparison of biochemical values in dialysis and non-dialysis patients in different nutritional groups.

Serum Albumin (gm/dl) mean

	Dialysis	Non-Dialysis	P-value
Normal nutrition	3.5±0.2	3.6±0.3	0.167
Mild to moderate malnutrition	3.3±0.3	3.7±0.2	0.038

Hemoglobin (gm/dl) mean:

	Dialysis	Non-Dialysis	P-value
Normal nutrition	9.1±0.8	11.8±1.1	0
Mild to moderate malnutrition	8.8±0.8	9.1±1.1	0.2

Mean BMI, MAMC, serum albumin, and hemoglobin decreased in non-dialysis CKD patients as the stages progressed (Table 7).

Table-7: Comparison of anthropometric and biochemical values in different stages of non-dialysis CKD patients

variables	Stage III	Stage IV	Stage V	p-value
Albumin	3.6±0.1	3.3±0.2	3.1±0.2	0
Hemoglobin	12.6±0.9	10.8±0.7	8.7±0.7	0
BMI	22±1.5	21.47±1.2	20.17±2.2	0.0023
MAMC	25.01±3.1	25.23±2.9	22.79±3.3	0.025

DISCUSSION

This study found that malnutrition was more prevalent in dialysis patients than in non-dialysis CKD patients. Similarly, it was found that as the disease progressed in CKD patients who were not under dialysis, the prevalence of malnutrition increased. No patients were found to have severe malnutrition.

In Nepal, there were studies done on hemodialysis patients using the SGA method and anthropometric and biochemical values to assess their nutritional status. In a study done by Arunsedhai et al. in 2015, 66.7% of study populations on hemodialysis were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition using the modified SGA method.^[9] There has not been any comparative study in Nepal to assess the nutritional status of CKD patients in dialysis and non-dialysis. In this study, using the SGA method, 77.03% of hemodialysis patients were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition compared to non-dialysis CKD patients, where 39.13% had mild to moderate malnutrition, which was statistically significant (p-value 0.000009).

Once CKD progresses to ESRD and patients initiate maintenance dialysis, their dietary protein intake increases, at least during the first year of therapy.^[10] Despite an increase in dietary protein and energy intake after initiation of dialysis, a high prevalence of poor nutritional status is developed, which suggests that protein-energy malnutrition alone does not explain the poor nutritional status in dialysis patients. The aggravated nutritional status in dialysis patients seems to be associated with the dialysis procedure and more advanced uremia. During standard HD treatment using high-flux dialyzers, approximately 8 g of free amino acids are removed.^[11] In addition, HD is known as a catabolic procedure, evidenced by the fact that patients on dialysis days are in negative nitrogen balance, even with high levels of protein intake.

In this study, 39.3% of CKD patients who were not under dialysis were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition using the SGA method. Of stage III, IV, and V CKD patients, all the patients of stage V were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition, 24 % of stage IV were found to have mild to moderate malnutrition, and none of the stage III patients were malnourished (p-value 0.0000). The reasons for this disparity could be multifactorial, including the patient's co-morbidities and the cause of their CKD, which shows how their disease was progressing, and nutritional factors like limiting protein intake in patients with nephrotic range proteinuria. Studies have found that restricting protein intake could be the leading cause of malnutrition in CKD patients owing to their increased catabolic rate. Patients with CKD should have at least 1-1.2gm/kg of daily protein intake in their diet; this high requirement might not be possible for our population because of poor economic status and below-par knowledge regarding their diet. During the initial period of the disease, where the fall in GFR is gradual, most people don't have any symptoms. As the GFR falls below 30, i.e., in stage IV of CKD, patients begin to experience uremic symptoms in the form of nausea, vomiting, and a decrease in appetite compounded by a high inflammatory state leading to a state of catabolism. This is more evident when the GFR falls below 15, and patient symptoms usually improve after they are dialyzed.^[12-14]

Anthropometry has long been used as an indicator of nutritional status because it is non-invasive and less expensive. Anthropometric measurements like BMI, MAMC, TSF thickness, and MUAC are being used to assess the nutritional status of patients. In this study, BMI and MAMC were measured in all the patients, and their mean was categorized along with the nutritional status of patients in both dialysis and non-dialysis groups. The mean MAMC was higher in the non-dialysis group than in the dialysis group, both in patients with normal nutrition (p-value 0.001) and mild to moderate malnutrition (p-value 0.038). However, there was no statistically significant result in our study comparing the BMI in dialysis and non-dialysis groups. In the non-dialysis group, mean BMI and MAMC were higher in the initial stage of the disease, and they reduced as the disease progressed, with a p-value of 0.0023 and 0.025, respectively. A study by Liman and his colleagues also reported that malnutrition was seen in 17.7% of patients with CKD based on BMI and the basis of MUAC, 51% of the patients were malnourished in their study done in Nigerian patients.^[15]

Low albumin is only seen when PEM manifests overtly. Serum albumin of more than 3.5gm/dl is considered optimal, while less than 3.5gm/dl is sub-optimal.^[16] In our study, the patients with normal nutrition had a mean serum albumin level of 3.54 gm/dl in hemodialysis patients compared to 3.62 gm/dl in non-dialysis patients (p-value 0.167), which is not statistically significant. Similarly, the mean serum albumin was sub-optimal in both groups of patients with mild to moderate malnutrition (p-value 0.038). In non-dialysis patients, the mean serum albumin was 3.6gm/dl, 3.3gm/dl, and 3.1gm/dl in stages III, IV, and V, respectively (p-value 0.0000). A similar observation was documented previously in some parts of China by Zhang et al., in which they had reported 53.72% of CKD patients with albumin levels below 3.5 gm/dl.^[17]

Patients with CKD have anemia of various severity as the disease progresses. During the initial stage, where the hemoglobin level is normal or low normal, as explained by compensatory mechanisms, patients often are asymptomatic. An essential factor in maintaining erythropoiesis is the production of a hormone called erythropoietin by the peritubular capillaries of the kidney. As CKD progresses, there is interstitial fibrosis and tubular atrophy, leading to loss of peritubular capillaries, eventually leading to a relative or absolute deficiency of erythropoietin. As the blood level of urea increases, it can cause direct toxicity to the marrow, causing ineffective erythropoiesis, bleeding diathesis, and anemia. In hemodialysis patients, blood is gradually lost during dialysis, accompanied by the inflammatory state aggravating the anemia. Other causes, like lack of dietary intake and malabsorption, are equally evident.^[8] In this study, the mean hemoglobin level decreased as the disease progressed in non-dialysis CKD patients (p-value 0.0000). The mean hemoglobin in patients who were normally nourished had a mean Hb of 11.8 gm/dl in a non-dialysis group compared to the dialysis with a mean Hb of 9.1gm/dl (p-value 0.0000). In patients with mild to moderate malnutrition, both the groups had mean Hb, which was statistically insignificant (p-value 0.20).

This study showed that the prevalence of malnutrition is common in CKD patients, as supported by other studies. The patients who are under hemodialysis are more malnourished as compared to those who are not under dialysis. In

non-dialysis patients, as the disease progresses, the patients are more malnourished. This is true for all CKD patients, as demonstrated by other studies.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

There were a few limitations of the study. The dietary intake of the patients was not considered, which could have been the factor causing malnutrition. Recall of dietary intake was not feasible and is cumbersome for most patients, so this study did not consider it. The educational and socioeconomic status of an individual plays a vital role in gaining insight into a patient's own disease condition and possible ways of tackling it. The patient's knowledge regarding protein intake and restriction was not assessed, which could be a limiting factor. It was not an age or sex-matched study; matching could have removed some bias.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of malnutrition was higher in dialysis patients than in non-dialysis CKD patients in Patan Hospital. Also, the nutritional assessment parameters used in this study were reliable, inexpensive, and easy to perform. The prevalence of malnutrition in CKD patients should lead the clinician to identify the cause of malnutrition in each individual. All the patients of CKD should be assessed from the very beginning, as early as stage 3, regarding their nutritional status using various parameters. Identifying the inflammatory state, halting the progression of the disease, correcting hypoalbuminemia, identifying the cause of anemia, and treating properly should be initiated as early as possible to reduce morbidity and mortality in these patients. Incorporating a dietician would be paramount in providing adequate knowledge and a dietary chart to every individual in preventing and managing malnutrition.

Dietary recommendations for hemodialysis patients include 1.2gm/kg protein daily; at least 50% should be high biological value. 30 to 35 Kcal/Kg of calories per day. Similarly, in patients with eGFR < 60ml/min, with non-nephrotic range proteinuria, protein intake of 0.8gm/kg/day is recommended.^[8]

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest or competing interests.

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